

DYNAMIC IN-PLANE RESPONSE OF HYBRID CELLS' HONEYCOMB

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ABSTRACT

The influence of the hybrid honeycomb cells that is cell having unique property of partial positive poisson's ratio and partial negative poisson's ratio under the dynamic in-plane crushing is studied by means of the explicit dynamic finite element simulation using ABAQUS. Auxetic structures offer a unique mechanical properties, volume change control and excellent impact energy absorption performance for multiple engineering applications. A cell having a controllable auxetic nature for a period of time along with the regular cell honeycombs can give advantage of better impact and crushing response. A comparative study of in-plane uniaxial compression loading behavior of regular honeycomb and hybrid cell was performed and deformation and failure modes are investigated under in-plane loading conditions. The effect of cell shape and the negative poisson ratio induced angle β is evaluated for different impact speeds and energy absorption results are plotted.

1 INTRODUCTION

Cellular materials have huge application areas due to superior energy absorption and impact resistance. Honeycomb structures have high stiffness and strength when loaded along out-of-plane direction, because the deformations require axial extension or compression of the strong cel walls. In contrast, in-plane stiffness and strength of honeycomb structures are much lower because in-plane stresses make the cell walls bend [1]. Different geometrical parameters effect are investigated by different researchers like cell shape, regular and irregular cell geometry, gradient thickness and cell wall angles along with imperfections [2-4]. On the other hand auxetic cellular materials are also investigated for their geometry and its effect on energy absorption response [5].

In this study, a unique cell shape is formulated which can exhibit auxetic nature for a specific time of load application and then can behave as a positive poisson ratio material as shown in Fig. 1. The in-plane numerical response is determined for multiple load cases with varying velocity from low to high and cell deformation and energy absorption characteristics are determined. A mathematical expression for proposed cell is derived in section 2 of the research. Lastly, an attempt is made to enhance the idea efficiency using different parameters like the negative poisson ratio induced angle β and further possible shapes on required parameters as per applications. The boundary conditions for this study are shown in Fig. 2.

Figure 1: Proposed cell geometry

Figure 2: Boundary Conditions

2 RESULTS

Deformation mode and load displacement curve for one of the possible configuration of the proposed cell geometry is shown in Fig. 3. The load displacement curve is plotted in Fig. 4. A comparison with the regular cell honeycomb and effect on deformation modes and energy absorption with defined parameters is also studied.

Figure 3: Deformation Mode

Figure 4: Load Displacement in X2

3 CONCLUSIONS

An attempt is made to combine the negative and positive Poisson's ratio in a controlled manner and to observe its effect on deformation modes and energy absorption using a cell having the defined abilities at the same time. The results indicate that such configurations have a margin to be investigated further and be implemented in a practical way. The manufacturing is simple and a small modification in the manufacturing technique can play the trick. This study can open a way to find out its further applications as per requirements.

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